

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.0614 Max: 63.3891	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1182 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	 University of Michigan Kelsey Museum of Archaeology Gabii Project
	In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 686-687	
DEFINITION Soil in corridor between SU 1183 and SU 1186			Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1165		Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay 80% silt 20% sand ___% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
			Compaction		Color	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft		<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		cut by cappuccina tomb		
Southern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
Western Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
Eastern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:			Abuts:			
Is covered by: SU 1165			Covers: 12,15			
Is cut by: 7791			Cuts:			
Is filled by:			Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS The soil fills the corridor that sits between the western wall of room 1 SU 1183 and the eastern wall of room 2 SU 1186; Also cut at southern end by cappuccina tomb						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: south central Shape: The soil fills a corridor of narrow rectilinear shape; a rectangle longer in length than it is wide						
For layers complete this section: Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): slightly southward Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): soil is composed of small rubble and granular silt - inclusions are densest at center and southern end Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): fairly even, but decreases in central area of the SU which corresponds to intrusion cut SU Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> other (specify) Difficult to determine w/out removing the soil						
For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North): Length of corridor 6.08m ↑ N ← SU 1183 cut SU 1191 Fill SU 1190 SU 1186 tile			

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

The soil SU 1182 appears to cover a narrow corridor that is located between the eastern wall of room 2 SU 1186 and western wall of room 1 SU 1183.
 The chronological relationship of the room walls is not yet clear

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by Megan Goldman-Petri

on 15/07/10

Revised by CMH

on 22.7.2010

PDFd by JJM

on 23.7.2010

Entered by

on